

Exploring Iris.ai and Yewno.discover with a Hackathon and expert quality assessment

AI & research support: Literature search

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Dansk resumé

Hensigten med projektet har været at undersøge hvorvidt to forskellige søgesystemer, der er bygget op om kunstig intelligens (KI), er anvendelige for forskere og studerende til akademisk informationssøgning. I undersøgelsen har projektet udført tænke-højt-tests med informationsspecialister (Appendix 1) samt et Hackathon, som denne rapport fremfører konklusionerne af.

Hensigten med at afholde et Hackathon med forskere og informationsspecialister, har været at se på om søgesystemer, der bygger på KI, er effektive i en forskningskontekst – herunder særligt med henblik på at fremsøge relevant materiale i systemerne. Desuden har projektet ville identificere anvendeligheden og værdien af systemerne for disse brugergrupper.

Projektets Hackathon blev afholdt i november 2021 og deltagerne var en blanding af informationsspecialister og forskere inden for forskellige områder. De blev inddelt i 4 grupper og fordelt på hhv. de to KI-systemer: Iris.ai og Yewno.discover, samt en kontrolgruppe, der søgte i Pubmed, Google Scholar og Web og Science. I grupperne blev der arbejdet sammen om et forskningsspørgsmål, der byggede på en præ-defineret case (Appendix 2). Målet var at finde max 10 relevante artikler, der kunne besvare forskningsspørgsmålet.

I løbet af de 4 timer det planlagte Hackathon varede, gennemgik grupperne en arbejdsproces, der både var fyldt med frustration, humor og fortvivlelse. Særligt vakte Iris.ai og Yewno.discover frustration i grupperne, da gennemsigtigheden og forståelsen af systemernes algoritmer var svære at afkode.

Gruppernes fremfundne artikler blev efterfølgende vurderet af en række forskere og informationsspecialister, der sammenholdt forskningsspørgsmålene med de fundne artikler. Ligeledes blev artiklerne underlagt en bibliometrisk analyse af projektgruppen. Ekspertbedømmelsen af artikler viste, at artiklerne, der var identificeret i forbindelse med søgninger i KI-systemerne, fik en lavere score i "tillid til artiklens resultater og konklusioner".

Konklusionen på Hackathon er, at Iris.ai og Yewno.discover er effektive værktøjer til at undersøge og udforske et emne samt til at visualisere en søgning, men de viser sig ikke "efficient", transparente eller som troværdige akademiske søgeværktøjer.

Ligeledes tvinger brugen af KI-værktøjer informationsspecialisten og forskeren til at indtage en ny tilgang til søgning, hvor brugen af boolske operatorer og systematik, må skubbes i baggrunden. Denne refleksion kan føre til en anderledes måde at tænke informationssøgning, som kræver ny terminologi, forståelse og forventninger til søgning samt nye kompetencerne hos dem, der søger.

Projektets Hackathon viser, at vi må opnå mere viden om systemarkitektur, kildekritik og andre relevante kompetencer, der er nødvendige for at kunne anvende systemerne i akademiske søgninger.

Introduction

The overall aim of this project is to investigate the extent different artificial intelligence (AI) powered search software support researchers and students in academic literature search. Our findings will inform future services at the university libraries affiliated to the Royal Library in Denmark.

Support through searching using AI-powered technologies can be provided in a multitude of ways – through saving time, through searching more efficiently and effectively, through providing new avenues of discovery and through transparency and documentation. We have a working hypothesis in the project that different types of users (student, senior researchers and library staff) place different values on different types of support. In the first delivery project we stated how AI-powered search is actually defined within the confines of the project, and which AI-software will be tested and why, (Wildgaard, Johnsen, & Kiersgaard, 2020). The chosen software, Iris.ai and Yewno.discover, has been tested throughout the Spring/Summer of 2021 in Think-Aloud tests with information specialists as test-participants. The aim, to investigate the AI-systems from a search professional point of view, (Appendix 1). The results of the think-aloud tests showed that information specialists are influenced by their background in information science, where they work in curated databases with block searches, thesauri and document representations. It is immediately clear that the test systems presented a whole new way of working with information retrieval and literature reviews. Our test subjects found it interesting to dive into these systems, but it frustrated them that they could not understand what was going on "behind the scenes" and in the "engine room". Understanding the system architecture is a very important aspect for information specialists in relation to teaching, support, and being able to provide high-quality professional search and research support. Both Iris.ai and Yewno.discover confronted the professional competence of our test subjects and challenged search methodology and research integrity, specifically transparency and documentation. These results challenge the use of AI-systems in a library context as new definitions and requirements to an academic search need to be defined.

In the Think-aloud tests the focus was on the functionality of the systems. We were not able to analyze the extent the goals of an academic search based on a well-defined research question are supported by the AI systems. Neither could we test how these systems create value for users. Therefore, in the Autumn of 2021, we invited researchers and information specialists to a Hackathon, where we had the opportunity to learn more about the efficiency and relevance of AI-powered search systems in "real-life" academic search, where transparency, reproducibility, stability, documentation and reliability are key. A Hackathon is a hosted event where participants work in collaboration to rapidly complete set tasks and solve problems. Traditionally these events have a competitive element, where tasks could be to design products or develop systems, for example Rys (2021) and Falk Olesen & Halskov (2020). Hackathons have also been applied in another context as a "Science Hackathons" (Schoeb et al, 2020; Wu et al, 2018) and are being used to provide learning and knowledge exchange opportunities, to create new and enhance existing social connections, and to investigate new technical opportunities (Pe-Than, et al 2019). A Hackathon demands careful planning and explicit goals. Our goal was to use the Hackathon event to challenge participants to be creative in their searches, apply their analytical skills and at the same time deliver insights in to their needs for AI-enhanced literature search support at the library.

Overall project objectives and research questions

The objectives of the project operationalised in the Hackathon are 1) to identify AI-powered search systems that support efficient and relevant outcomes for academic searchers, and 2) Ensure the usefulness of the AI-powered search system for diverse user-groups (information specialists, students, Ph.D., researchers and other disciplines). Accordingly, the Hackathon set-up attempts to answer the following questions:

- Are the AI-powered search systems Iris.ai and Yewno.discover more efficient than traditional search resources, PubMed, Web of Science and Google Scholar?
- Which value does Iris.ai and Yewno.discover add to the academic search process for users?
- Which value does Iris.ai and Yewno.discover add to the academic search process for information professionals?

Method

Hackathon

The design of the Hackathon is adapted from (Schoeb et al, 2020). Participants were divided into four groups, Table 1. Group 1, searched in Iris.ai, Group 2, searched Yewno.discover, Group 3, Iris.ai and Yewno.discover and Group 4 was the control group which searched in structured databases and platforms PubMed, Web of Science and Google Scholar. Whereas Groups 1, 2 and 4 were a mix of information specialists and researchers, Group 3 consisted only of information specialists. This to investigate if information specialists can return just as relevant results from AI-powered search as the mixed groups. All groups worked on the same problem statement (Appendix 2) and were required to develop their own research question and consequently design their own search in the system they were assigned to.

Prior to the Hackathon all participants were invited to an introductory webinar in each of the AI-powered search systems. Supplementary learning material was also provided. Further, they were invited to complete a short introductory survey (Appendix 3) enquiring into their knowledge and skills in information seeking, their knowledge/experience in the test systems, and other demographic information (institutional affiliation, status as researcher or information specialist) Table 1.

The Hackathon was held at Aarhus University Library, on the 8th of November 2021, 11:15 am to 4:00 pm. The library provided ample space for the groups to work independently and come together as a collective for lunch, breaks and discussions. Each group had the opportunity to use large screens in their work, whiteboards and other note taking materials were provided. Each participant brought their own computer, and personal access to the search systems was provided and tested before the Hackathon. On the day of the Hackathon, the participants were introduced to the project and the main objectives. Lunch was provided and then the Hackathon search event began. The participants were divided into predefined groups to ensure compatibility within the groups and homogeneity across the groups. Three groups consisted of junior and senior researchers, and information specialists. The aim was to represent a research team construction. The fourth group was made up of information specialists alone (Table 1).

Table 1: participant demographics and group assignment

Group	System	Title*	Specialty	Experience SR**	Experience Iris.ai/Yewno
1	Iris.ai	I	Health	Good	Beginner
1	Iris.ai	R	Health	Good	Beginner
1	Iris.ai	I	Health	Expert	Beginner
1	Iris.ai	R	Health	Good	Beginner
2	Yewno.discover	R	Business and social science	Intermediate	Beginner
2	Yewno.discover	I	Natural Science & Technology	Expert	Beginner
2	Yewno.discover	R	Business and social science	Intermediate	Beginner
2	Yewno.discover	I	Business and social science	Expert	Beginner
3	Iris.ai & Yewno.discover	I	Business and social science	Expert	Beginner
3	Iris.ai & Yewno.discover	I	Natural Science & Technology	Good	Beginner
4	Control	I	Health	Expert	Beginner
4	Control	I	Health	Expert	Beginner
4	Control	R	Health	Good	Beginner
4	Control	R	Health	Good	Beginner
4	Control	R	Health	Good	Beginner

* R = researcher, I = information specialist

**Participants' subjective evaluation of skills in systematic search and review

The control group, Group 4, searched in PubMed, Web of Science and Google Scholar

The three research team groups searched in Iris.ai (Group 1), Yewno.discover (Group 2) or a combination of PubMed, Google Scholar and Web of Science, as a control group (Group 4). The information specialist group (Group 3) searched in both AI-systems (Iris.ai and Yewno.discover). Throughout the day four independent observers noted the interaction within the groups using a preset observation template (Appendix 4). Throughout the Hackathon the participants were encouraged to take breaks whenever they needed to, refreshments were provided ad libitum likewise they were encouraged to step away from their computers to discuss their next steps in the search process.

The same case and definition of research task was issued to all participants (Appendix 2). Each group was provided with a collection of documents on a shared Google Drive, to help them document their search. This document collection consisted of:

- The case and definition of research task (Appendix 2)
- A reflection document template to record the research question, search terms, the steps in the search process and explain choices made during the search. The reflection document was tailored to fit the system the group searched in (Appendix 5 - 7)
- A standardized report formula in which to record the bibliographic information and a short description of up to 10 relevant articles found during the search (Appendix 8)

Therefore, the tasks each group were required to complete during the Hackathon were to:

- Understand the case
- Define a research question(s)
- Search in the systems
- Document the search process and choices made throughout the search
- Screen and select up to 10 relevant publications found during the search.

After the Hackathon, a debriefing survey was sent to the participants to enquire further into their search experience and considerations (Appendix 9 -10). Participants were asked to rate their satisfaction with each system, the effectivity of the search, the effectivity of discovery, and if they would use the systems again, either in a guidance with students and researchers or just as general resource in their searches. The participants were encouraged to qualify their answers with free text comments.

The observational data were analyzed using methods from Stanford University's "Design Thinking Bootcamp Bootleg" (<https://dschool.stanford.edu/resources/the-bootcamp-bootleg>) specifically "Story-share & Capture" and "Saturate & Group". In "Story share & Capture" the investigative team shares observations and experiences. One project member at a time talked out from their observational notes taken during the Hackathon, while the other members posted on a Padlet (Padlet.com), noting down the main themes and experiences they heard from the "Storyteller". After which, there was the opportunity to probe for more information. When all project members had presented their observations and where exhausted for information the next step was to "Saturate and Group" the posts on the Padlet. By grouping the posts into themes and sub-themes, patterns emerge and meaningful insights and needs of the Hackathon participants could be identified. The grouping of themes is also useful to find similarities and differences between the tested AI-systems and user-groups.

Quality Assessment

A committee of experts with experience in scientific communication and research integrity/methodologies evaluated and ranked publications selected as relevant by the participants. The experts were researchers and information specialists from the health and natural sciences employed at university hospitals and university libraries. The experts were invited by email to read up to three publications each. Included in the invitation was the case (Appendix 2) and the group's research question. The experts were not informed if the publications were found in the AI-powered search system or in the control systems, PubMed and Google Scholar.

Based on their assessment of the scientific conduct and integrity of the publication, the experts were instructed to rate out of ten the extent they trusted the results and the conclusions drawn in each publication. They were asked to indicate the relevance of the publication to the research question posed by the group during the Hackathon, and in summary, stating if they felt the publication was "spot on". The responses were collected in a standardized survey in SurveyXact (Appendix 11).

Quantity Assessment

A quantitative assessment of the found publications collected information about the publishing source of each relevant publication. The title of the publication was noted, a DOI to ensure verification during the quality assessment (not included in the table), the language of the

publication, publication type (original article, editorial, meeting report, etc.), the methodology employed in the article, the publishing source, publisher, type of peer review process, if support for the peer reviewers was offered, and if the journal is open access, Table 7.

In a bibliometric description, all publishing sources were identified in Web of Science (accessed through the Royal Danish Library, November 2021) and the following bibliometric information recorded: publication year, Web of Science Research Area, 2-year journal impact factor, Field Quartile, Article Impact Factor, and total number of citations to each publication. The level of each publication registered on the Danish Research Indicator was also collected (Table 8).

Description of test software

Iris

<https://iris.ai/>

Iris.ai navigates Open Access literature, primarily in the disciplines of health and chemistry, but also in other sources that can be tailored to fit the users' needs. Topic modelling and "finger printing" technology is used to display results to the user in topic maps, which the user can then filter their way through to increase specificity. Iris.ai offers free and paid versions of the product, that allow to varying degrees, according to negotiation with the vendor, integration with organisational and subscription databases, collaboration and multi-user functionalities, relevance filters, bookmarking, the possibility to establish inclusion and exclusion criteria to the search, import functions and RSS feeds. Iris.ai can be integrated with reference managers.

Access to iris.ai was through e-mail domain recognition at the Royal Library. From AU and KU users were upgraded by Iris.ai administrator by request.

Yewno.discover

<https://www.yewno.com/>

Yewno.discover is a multidisciplinary tool that enables the user to search using ideas and concepts rather than keywords. It is designed as a way to develop questions in research projects and get the user to think about the vocabulary they use to frame their work. Technically, this means that fulltext analysis is conducted through the use of computational semantics, neural networks, & Machine-Learning. In a graphic display of results in a concept map, important nodes of concepts are differentiated from ideas related to the concept. The maps are presented in defined contexts, and change according to the context the user finds most useful. Access to the literature is gained by clicking on the nodes on the map. Yewno can be integrated with the library's other discovery services, and can search in academic or government documents published in English, German or Chinese.

Access through IP-address recognition (and VPN) for the Royal Library

Control group: Pubmed, Google Scholar and Web of Science

The control group was made up of databases and platforms traditionally used in academic searches. The aim was to observe how participants perform an academic search in known resources that support search methods, including Boolean search, controlled index terms, keywords and proximity

operators. Hence, we aim to establish what changes might occur in information behaviour during an academic search in AI-powered systems versus traditional sources.

PubMed

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

PubMed is a free interface to search Medline. It contains over 3,500 journals published internationally, covering all areas of medicine and includes the entire Medline database (1966+) PLUS PreMedline (recent articles that are not yet fully indexed for Medline) as well as links to access to full-text web sites through the Royal Library. PubMed can be searched using MeSH terms, author names, title words, text words or phrases, journal names, or any combination of these. Users can register for an NCBI profile where they can save search histories, update searches and create alerts. Search results can be exported in a variety of ways, compatible with multiple reference management and review management tools. Please note, the search is primarily based on matching terms in document representations and tables of terms rather than full text.

Access through login via the Royal Library, Copenhagen University Library or Aarhus University library dependent on the affiliation of the participant.

Web of Science

<https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/solutions/web-of-science/>

Web of Science is a platform that provides access to a collection of interdisciplinary, bibliographic citation databases with references from journals, books, proceedings, and conferences. It is possible to search for subjects, authors and institutions and follow links to citing and cited references. Further, one can assess the impact of a specific article, author or institution measures by number of citations and various other citation and impact factors. Web of Science can be searched using field specific searches in representations of the indexed papers, such author, title, journal name, ISSN, research area (as defined by Web of Science), keywords and year. Search history can be saved if the user has a profile and search results can be exported in various formats and enriched various descriptive data, such as citations, references and bibliometric indicators.

Login via the Royal Library, KU or AU allowed the participants seamless access to fulltext materials in the library catalogue and databases in the Web of Science platform

Google Scholar

<https://scholar.google.com/>

Google Scholar is a freely accessible web search engine that indexes the full text or metadata of scholarly literature from all disciplines, academic sources and in different formats. The engine can be searched using basic Boolean, quotation marks to define a phrase, descriptors and a character limit of 256 signs. Search results are displayed most relevant first, calculated on the extent the searched terms match the item's full text, author, source and the number of times it has been cited. Search results can be saved to a reading list, and up to ten results (including fulltext if available to the user) at a time can be exported if the user creates a profile. By activating the link to the Royal Library in Google Scholar's settings, the participant could link to full text in the Library catalogue as well as publically available databases.

Login with Google-account, and in settings, ensure linking to the Royal Library is activated.

Results

Post-interview with the participants

The participants (P1-P6 in each AI-search system only, *r* = researcher, *i*= information specialist) completed a short survey, investigating their experience in and opinion of Iris.ai or Yewno.discover. They were asked their opinion of the system’s ability to support a systematic search, provided an effective way to search, an effective way to explore a theme or area, the quality of found articles, if they would use the system again either in a teaching/supervision scenario or in their own work as an information specialist or researcher. Their answers were coded on a 4-point scale, Tables 2 and 4. The overall satisfaction with the search experience in the system was measured on a five-point scale, where 1 was the lowest rate, Tables 3 and 5.

Iris.ai

Iris.ai was not considered to support a systematic or effective approach to searching by either researchers or information specialists. Two participants saw a potential in Iris.ai to support an effective approach to exploring a theme or an area, (P2*i* and P5*r*). Satisfaction with the quality of the retrieved articles was rated as ≤ 1 .

Table 2. Assessments of Iris.ai

	P1 <i>r</i>	P2 <i>i</i>	P3 <i>i</i>	P4 <i>i</i>	P5 <i>r</i>	P6 <i>i</i>	mean (range)	Mean <i>r</i> n2	Mean <i>i</i> n4
Support systematic search	1	1	1	1	2	2	1.3 (1-2)	1.5	1.25
Effective search	1	1	1	1	3	1	1.3 (1-3)	2	1
Effective exploration	1	2	1	1	3	1	1.5 (1-3)	2	1.25
Article quality	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.67 (0-1)	1	0.5
Use in teaching	1	1	1	1	1	1	1 (1)	1	1
Use again	1	1	1	1	3	1	1.3 (1-3)	2	1

Scale: no =1, Partly = 2, Yes=3, Don't know = 0

The participants were asked to explain the purpose of Iris.ai in their own words. The researchers understood Iris.ai as a system that provided “a different way to find relevant literature”, (P1*r*), which “...promotes the encounter with literature that one is not necessarily aware one is seeking”, (P5*r*). Iris.ai was also noted to encourage a creative process that “contributes to you as a literature seeker becoming sharper on what you are actually looking for” (P5*r*). The information specialists stated the purpose of Iris.ai was to “discover relevant articles that are not sought systematically and with few search terms”, (P2*i*), and uses “other search techniques than in traditional database searches” (P3*i*, P4*i*). P6*i* commented that the main purpose of Iris.ai is to speed-up the search process and provide a

quick and easy way to find literature. However, P6i also noted that they did not experience this intended speed and ease of search during the Hackathon.

When asked to comment on how well the search process was documented in Iris.ai, researchers and information specialists were in agreement that documentation was insufficient, especially if the intention was to document a systematic search (P3i).

Table 3: Overall satisfaction

	P1r	P2i	P3i	P4i	P5r	P6i	mean (range)	Mean r n2	Mean i n4
Satisfaction	2	2	2	1	3	3	2.17(1-3)	2.5	2

Satisfaction scale: 1=very dissatisfied, 2= dissatisfied, 3= OK, 4= satisfied, 5=Very satisfied

The participants gave Iris.ai an overall satisfaction rating between 1 and 3, indicating general dissatisfaction with the system, $\bar{x} = 2.17$, (1-3), Table 3. They would not use Iris.ai in a teaching or guidance situation, though one researcher, P5r, would use Iris.ai again in their own research practices and could see a value in the system for PhD-students. The remaining participants did not see any value in using Iris.ai at all, but were cautious in their conclusion due to the limited amount of time they had had to learn and work with Iris.ai.

Yewno.discover

Yewno.discover was considered by the information specialists, P1i, P2i, P3i and P6i to partially support a systematic approach to searching, Table 4, but was not considered an effective way to search, rating ≤ 1 or explore a theme or an area by P1i, P2i and P6i, rating 1,1,2. Researchers, P4r, and P5r did not consider Yewno.discover to support either a systematic or effective search, respectively, 1,2 and 1,1. P5r agreed with P3i that the system provided an effective way to explore a theme or area, giving the top rate of 3. Satisfaction with the quality of the retrieved articles was rated between 2 and 3 by the information specialists, whereas the researchers were dissatisfied or unable to judge, P4r and P5r respectively rating 1 and do not know. The majority of the participants would use Yewno.discover again in teaching or in their own research practice and saw a value for users independent of academic seniority, students and researchers, as Yewno.discover supports exploration in a subject. Thus, the value is dependent on when Yewno.discover is used in the research process.

The information specialists explained the purpose of Yewno.discover as to “qualify the explorative phase at the start of a search”, (P1i), and “identify terms and conduct simple topic searches in a simple and intuitive way, that can be described using only two terms”, (P2i, P6i). Further, they commented the purpose of Yewno.discover was to “test a new technology in a literature review”, (P3r). Researchers considered the purpose of Yewno.discover to be “a search engine, that helps explore concepts and relationships between these concepts, potentially across research domains”, (P4r and P5r). Both P1i and P5r noted the usefulness of Yewno.discover as a person new to a research area.

Table 4: Assessments of Yewno.discover

	P1i	P2i	P3i	P4r	P5r	P6i	Overall mean (range)	Mean r n2	Mean i n4
Support systematic	2	2	1	1	2	2	1.67 (1-2)	1.5	1.75
Effective search	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.83 (0-1)	1	0.75
Exploration	1	1	3	1	3	2	1.83 (1-3)	2	1.75
Article quality	2	3	3	0	1	2	1.83 (0-3)	0.5	2.5
Use in teaching	2	1	2	1	2	3	1.83 (1-3)	1.5	2
Use again	3	3	3	1	3	3	2.67 (1-3)	2	3

Scale: no =1, Partly = 2, Yes=3, Don't know = 0

When asked their opinion about how well the search was documented in Yewno.discover the information specialists were in agreement that "...footsteps provides documentation of search activity" (P1i and P6i) but overall documentation is insufficient, (P2i). The researchers noted that even though the search activity was documented in footsteps, the search itself was not documented or transparent (P4r) and replication of the search was difficult (P5r).

Table 5: Overall satisfaction

	P1i	P2i	P3i	P4r	P5r	P6i	mean (range)	Mean r n3	Mean i n3
Satisfaction	4	3	3	2	4	4	3.3 (2-4)	3	3.5

Satisfaction scale: 1=very dissatisfied, 2= dissatisfied, 3= OK, 4= satisfied, 5=very satisfied

The participants gave Yewno.discover an overall satisfaction rating between 2 and 4, indicating that the system was an "OK" system, $\bar{x} = 3.3$, (2-4), Table 5. Information specialists were more satisfied with Yewno.discover than researchers, respective ratings $i=3,3,4,4$, $r=2,4$.

Observations from the Hackathon

The observations from the Hackathon were discussed within the project group using "Storyshare & Capture" methods, recording themes and experiences on a Padlet in January 2022: (Archived, and not available to share). The posts were grouped into candidate themes and child themes for each test group. Group 1 (Iris.ai), Group 2 (Yewno.discover), Group 3(Iris.ai/Yewno.discover) and Group 4 (Web of Science, Google Scholar and PubMed) using "Saturate & capture" methods.. Five candidate themes emerged and were detected across all groups (Methodology, Professionalism, Humour, Experience and Understanding the system). These are presented on the next page.

Methodology

Group 1's methodological approach to searching in Iris.ai, was to first search in PubMed to find papers relevant to the research question and then use concepts, terms and snippets from these articles to design the 500-word problem statement that is required in Iris.ai to start the search. The participants discussed the approach as a "backwards" design i.e. identifying search terms in the literature that in turn informed how the research question was formulated and operationalised as a search. The group experimented with repeating certain terms to weight their importance in the problem statement and hence improve the relevance of the search results.

Like Group 1, Group 2 deferred to PubMed as a gold standard to find concepts to kick-start the search. The search in Yewno.discover progressed quickly after the two major concepts were defined, and the iterative flow of reading articles and defining new search terms to direct the search happened intuitively. Group 3 found limiting the search to two concepts in Yewno.discover very challenging as the search case was very complex, containing multiple aspects. They expected to conduct a more specific search in Iris.ai, but commented that the requirement to provide a 500 word problem statement would be a huge barrier for searchers with limited or little knowledge on the subject of the search. Regarding the documentation of the search, Group 3 were satisfied that the knowledge maps in Yewno.discover provided proof of the scope of the search and the journey documented the steps they had taken. . However, for the documentation to be transparent and support replication, it needed to be enriched manually with extensive notes. However, the group were very concerned with the lack of documentation in Iris.ai.

Whereas Groups 1, 2 and 3 discussed the case and searched in the systems simultaneously, Group 4 discussed the case for a long time before designing a PICO search consisting of the most important concepts and search terms that were truncated and defined as MeSH or textwords. Search results were ranked using "best match" in PubMed and new terms identified. The search was adjusted accordingly and repeated. Group 4 also searched in Google Scholar, searching using terms identified in the PubMed search using Boolean logic. The block search in Google Scholar resulted in thousands of snippets, and the Group concentrated only on the first page. Limiting the search to specific fields in Google Scholar was explored, eg. "inTitle" but was judged to be too limiting.

Professionalism

Both Group 1, Group 2 and Group 4 divided responsibilities for the search between the different professional profiles within each group. The information specialists translated the research question into a search strategy, using field operators and Boolean logic where possible. They also conducted the search in the systems while the researchers defined and discussed the case and led the exploration of the results. However, Group 2, quickly began to work together as a team after the research question and concepts were defined, whereas Group 1 and Group 4 continued to divide the work throughout the Hackathon based on their expertise as information specialist or researcher. The control group, Group 4, were as traditional in their approach to the search as they were in their division of labour within the group. The information specialists implemented the same search string in Web of Science, PubMed and to the best of their abilities in Google Scholar. Terms and concepts were confirmed in PubMed, discussed with the researchers in the group and then translated by the information specialists into the search syntax and PICO befitting each system. A clear division of roles was thus observed, where the information specialist had the role of "technician" and the researcher "subject specialist".

Group 1 investigated how Iris.ai supported both an unstructured approach to the search in the Explore phase and a structured approach in the Focus phase. The group wanted to make the search more precise as the results were very broad and pointed in many different directions. The

information specialists found improving precision difficult. They needed a structure in Iris.ai that supports precision. They expressed concern about how to apply their knowledge of search theory and methods in Iris.ai and questioned how their search-commands were interpreted in the system. Similarly, Group 2 attempted to fit the block search method to Yewno.discover. However, Yewno.discover does not support Boolean and block searches and thus forced Group 2 to reluctantly reject known search tactics and search in a new way. Late in the Hackathon-day, they concluded that it was not beneficial to the search or their ambitions with the search to continuously compare the AI-system to Google Scholar or PubMed. They concluded that AI-systems present new ways to search, new possibilities and new understandings of an academic search and as such created new fundamental challenges to their professionalism.

Group 3 attempted to decipher if the lack of relevant and useable search results was due to the system's interpretation of the search question or their own incorrect use of the functions in the AI-systems. They began to doubt their own search rationale, which ultimately changed from a systematic approach to cherry picking.

Humour

The participants' humor was strongly affected by the system they searched in. The project group are aware that the Hackathon was a long day and participants were tired by the end, yet noticeable mood swings were observed that did not have anything to do with test fatigue.

Group 1 became increasingly frustrated with not being able to formulate a good problem statement of 500 words in Iris.ai. Group 2 were also very frustrated in being limited to two concepts in Yewno.discover. Two concepts were not considered enough to cover all the variables in their research question. Frustration was increased when the group accidentally deleted their "Journey" (search history) by clicking on the "back" button in the browser and refreshing the search. Accordingly, all their work, saved concepts, maps and articles were lost.

While Group 3's humour changed from positive to negative as the search progressed, Group 4, on the other hand, was engaged in the search from the beginning and approached the case as if the task was part of a real-life research project. Their humour was professional and positive as the search showcased their skills and areas of expertise and confirmed their knowledge of the search systems and case. The control-systems supported systematic approaches. The rationale for the interpretation of the search in each system was discussed and contributed to the validity of the overall search strategy. This group worked intensively and experienced test-fatigue towards the end of the day when the task was to select relevant publications and describe the type of publication, the method, which elements relevant to the case the paper covers and the key conclusions in the report template.

The search experience

Iris.ai was considered to provide an exciting interface but lacking in the necessary functions that the participants needed to conduct a systematic search (Group 1 and Group 3). Group 1 would have liked more time in the "Explore" phase to dive down into the connections between the concepts and underlying literature and struggled as a result with gaining an overview of the search results. Both groups had negative experiences with formulating the problem statement, and as the problem statement is so important for the identification of concepts would have liked to have received the case before the Hackathon-day, so they could formulate an appropriate statement. Particularly

Group 3 noted that Iris.ai demands a lot of knowledge about the topic area in order to produce a focused search.

The search interface in Yewno.discover was also considered inviting, user friendly and provided an intuitive approach to the search, (Groups 2 and 3). Group 2's experience was mainly frustration as described in the previous section regarding the stability of the system. They stopped relying on the system to document the search and instead took notes, copy/pasted concept definitions and steps in the search in a separate document. Group 3 were disappointed that Yewno.discover illustrated *possible* links between concepts on the knowledge map but did not provide publications that included both of these concepts, even though it was easy to find such publications in Google Scholar.

The control group, Group 4, were able to retrieve many publications and many of the same publications were identified in PubMed, Web of Science and Google Scholar. Their only frustration was that they ran out of time and their choice of relevant publications to send to expert assessment was not as considered as they would have liked it to be. They did however wonder why the search did not return "qualitative" publications and which sources they would have to search in to find this type of publication and hence improve the scope and integrity of the search.

System understanding

Group 1 and Group 3 concluded that the functionalities in Iris.ai hampered their professionalism, for example, they would have preferred to see all the entire result list at once rather than step-wise through the Focus phase. They could not make sense of the exclude/include options which they found very time consuming and were very frustrated with Iris.ai's relevance ranking, which the groups did not agree with at all. Particularly the groups discussed why Iris.ai presented so many irrelevant terms during the focus phase. Group 2 and Group 3 saw great potential in Yewno.discover - the system was visually inviting, navigation was user friendly, the idea of multi-select and layers made sense, the system encouraged discovery and there was a logic in combining and deleting concepts. However, in practice the multi-select disguised that the search still only found the presence of two concepts in a publication, it was unclear how the concepts were weighted in the search and the definition of a concept was not context dependent. Group 3 could not understand why Yewno.discover retrieved so few publications when they proved repeatedly that they could identify many relevant publications in Google Scholar. Finally, Group 4 displayed advanced knowledge of the searched systems, their algorithms, ranking and relevance parameters and system architecture. They even tested the systems against each other to confirm the precision and specificity of the search.

Quality assessment of retrieved articles

In total, the four groups identified 19 potentially relevant publications that were sent to the 14 experts for quality assessment. The publications were grouped into seven subject packages that the project group judged would appeal to the individual experts' specialist knowledge, meaning that each expert was invited to read two or three articles. Each package of publications was sent to two experts for independent assessment. 11/14 experts took part in the quality assessment, giving a 79% participation rate. Sixteen out of nineteen articles were assessed, giving a completion rate of 84%. The complete list of publications retrieved in the Hackathon are presented in Tables 7 and 8 as part of the quantitative analysis, where title, journal, publisher, method and study type are reported. The sixteen publications that were evaluated by the experts are presented below in Table 6. The experts assessed Group 1's one publication, 8/10 publications found by Group 2, the one publication found

by Group 3 and 6/7 publications found by Group 4. Trust in the results and conclusions were rated on a ten-point scale, where 1 = no trust and 10=complete trust. Relevance was rated on a 3-point scale, 1 = not relevant, 2=partially relevant and 3= relevant.

The experts' trust in the results and conclusions were marginally higher in Iris.ai than in the control. In Iris.ai the overall mean trust in results $\bar{x} = 8$ and conclusions $\bar{x}=7$, whereas in the control group, Group 4, trust in results $\bar{x} =7.4$ (range 2-10) and conclusions $\bar{x} = 6.8$ (range 2-10). Trust in the results and conclusions in the publications found by Group 2 and Group 3 were rated lowest. Group 2 scored an overall mean trust in results $\bar{x}=6.35$ (range 2-10) and trust in conclusions $\bar{x}=5.2$ (range 1-10). Group 3, who searched in both Iris.ai and Yewno.discover found their single publication in Yewno.discover, and similarly scored $\bar{x}=6$ and $\bar{x}=5.5$ in respectively trust in results and trust in conclusions. In the quantitative analysis, next section and Table 7, we identify the type of study each publication reports and it becomes clear that we are comparing the quality of editorials, meeting reports and original articles. Hence, if we compare trust in the publications that are identified as "original studies" (Group 2, articles 5, 6 and 7, Group 3, article 1 and Group 4, articles 1 – 6) we find that trust in results and conclusions is slightly higher in Group 2, respectively $\bar{x}=7$, and $\bar{x}=6.2$.

The articles found by Group 1, Group 2 and Group 3 in respectively Iris.ai, Yewno.discover or a combination of both AI-systems were judged not relevant for the research question, scoring an overall mean relevance score of Iris.ai=1, Yewno.discover = 1.2, Iris.ai and Yewno.discover = 1.5. The publications found by Group 4, control in PubMed and Google Scholar, were primarily judged relevant or partially relevant, overall mean relevance score = 2.5. All of the 10 publications found in the AI-powered systems were not considered "spot on" for answering the research question posed by the Hackathon groups. In contrast, five out of the six assessed publications identified by the control group, Group 4, were considered "spot on" by at least one expert.

Table 6: Expert quality assessment of retrieved publications

Group	Trust in results <i>expert 1, expert 2</i> (mean)	Trust in conclusion <i>expert 1, expert 2</i> (mean)	Relevance score <i>expert 1, expert 2</i> (mean)	Relevance	Spot on
Group 1 (Iris.ai)					
Article1	8, - (-)	7, - (-)	1, - (-)	not relevant	no
Group 2 (Yewno.discover)					
Article1	7, - (-)	1, - (-)	1, - (-)	not relevant	no
Article2	7, - (-)	1, - (-)	1, - (-)	not relevant	no
Article3	2, 5 ($\bar{x}=3.5$)	2, 5 ($\bar{x}=3.5$)	1, 1 ($\bar{x}=1$)	not relevant	no
Article4	6, 10 ($\bar{x}=8$)	7, 10 ($\bar{x}=8.5$)	1, 3 ($\bar{x}=2$)	not relevant/ relevant	no/yes
Article5	10, 5 ($\bar{x}=7.5$)	4, 5 ($\bar{x}=4.5$)	1, 1 ($\bar{x}=1$)	not relevant	no
Article6	6, 10 ($\bar{x}=8$)	6, 10 ($\bar{x}=8$)	1, 1 ($\bar{x}=1$)	not relevant	no
Article7	5, 6 ($\bar{x}=5.5$)	5, 7 ($\bar{x}=6$)	1, 2 ($\bar{x}=1.5$)	not relevant/ partially	no
Article8	8, 2 ($\bar{x}=5$)	8, 2 ($\bar{x}=5$)	1, 1 ($\bar{x}=1$)	not relevant	no
Group 3 (Iris.ai/Yewno.discover)					
Article1	5, 7 ($\bar{x}=6$)	5, 6 ($\bar{x}=5.5$)	2, 1 ($\bar{x}=1.5$)	partially/ not relevant	no
Group 4 (Control)					
Article1	9, - (-)	9, - (-)	3, - (-)	relevant	yes
Article2	9, 10 ($\bar{x}=9.5$)	9, 10 ($\bar{x}=9.5$)	3, 3 ($\bar{x}=3$)	relevant	yes
Article3	2, 9 ($\bar{x}=5.5$)	2, 9 ($\bar{x}=5.5$)	1, 2 ($\bar{x}=1.5$)	not relevant/ partially	no
Article4	8, 10 ($\bar{x}=9$)	8, 6 ($\bar{x}=7$)	3, 3 ($\bar{x}=3$)	relevant	yes
Article5	8, 3 ($\bar{x}=5.5$)	6, 2 ($\bar{x}=4$)	3, 2 ($\bar{x}=2.5$)	relevant/ partially	yes/no
Article6	5, 9 ($\bar{x}=7$)	5, 9 ($\bar{x}=7$)	2, 3 ($\bar{x}=2.5$)	partially /relevant	no/yes

Quantitative assessment of the retrieved articles

A description of each retrieved publication, including title, type (editorial, original article, etc), employed method (interview, questionnaire, RCT, etc), publishing journal, publisher, type of peer review, support offered for peer reviewers and Open Access is presented in Table 7. A bibliometric description of the retrieved articles, including year published, research area, field quartile, 2-year impact factor, total number of citations and BFI level are presented in Table 8. The bibliometric indicators and research areas are calculated in Journal Citation Reports¹ (Access through the Royal Library/Copenhagen University Library).

The two tables together indicate the prestige of the publishing journal, the integrity of the peer review process and the use of the publication. Further, the tables point to the “openness” of the publications, as the library that is funding this project would like to support the increased use of open access publications.

Eighteen out of the nineteen retrieved publications were written in English. However, one was an English abstract to a German publication. This publication was found in Iris and indexed based on its

¹ <https://jcr-clarivate-com.ep.fjernaadgang.kb.dk/jcr/home>

metadata and recorded in the system as an English language publication. Thirteen of the publications were original articles, predominantly interviews, cases, surveys and literature reviews. Three were opinion papers, one was an editorial and one a meeting report. Yewno.discover retrieved the greatest variety of publication types and variety of employed methods. All publishers across all groups are deemed reputable, primarily Springer, Elsevier and Wiley, and as such no difference in source quality is observed between the AI-systems and the control group. However, the type of peer review and availability of peer-review policy statements do appear to be of a lower standard in sources retrieved from Yewno.discover. Five out of the eleven publications identified in Yewno.discover did not use peer review or have an explicit peer review policy on the source website. However, Yewno.discover does appear to include publications from sources that support alternative forms of peer review and thus a more open and untraditional approach to the verification of science. Eleven of the nineteen publications were open access, eight of these were identified in Yewno.discover and the remaining three from the control group.

The bibliometric analysis indicated that the publications were published in 2020 or 2021 and came from diverse research areas. Publications identified in Iris.ai were ranked in the lowest journal quartile for that research area, calculated on 2-year journal impact factor for 2020, and cited below average (article citation score). Yewno.discover retrieved the majority of publications from sources ranked in the top quartile of their research area (5/10), three from the second quartile, and two from the third quartile. One publication was from a discontinued journal with no available bibliometric data.

Seven of the ten publications (70%) from Yewno.discover are cited more than the average publication published in the journal (article influence score) while 4 out of the seven publications (57%) found by the control group were cited more than average. Even though the publications were very recent, all of the publications identified by the control group, Group 4, had amassed some citations, min.=1, max.=240, median = 20; the publications from Yewno.discover received between 0 and 348 citations, median=1, mode=0 and the publication from Iris.ai had not received any citations at the time of the analysis.

The final analysis assessed if the publishing source was included on the authority lists of the Danish Bibliometric Indicator (BFI). Researchers in Denmark are encouraged to publish in sources included on this list, as the BFI is part of a distribution key that shares basic funding across the eight Danish universities. Level 2 is the highest level and rewards publications with the greatest amount of points which are translated at funds in the distribution key. The publication found in Iris.ai is not included on the BFI. Four of the eleven publications identified in Yewno.discover are included in the BFI on level 2, four are on level one and the remaining three are not included in the BFI. All of the publications identified by Group 4 are included in the BFI, three on level 2 and four on level one.

Discussion

The post-survey responses and observations from the Hackathon indicate that researchers and information specialists consider the purpose of Iris.ai and Yewno.discover to be tools for exploring, discovering and identifying new terms - and especially with a view to the initiation of a search process or investigation of a new research area. The participants were dissatisfied with Iris.ai and even though they experienced low specificity and low relevance in Yewno.discover, they were generally satisfied with the product and could see potential in the system.

The low rating of Iris.ai is due to the participants experiencing difficulties in controlling the search and narrowing the search which resulted in a limited amount of relevant articles being identified.

The participants felt that they were wasting time, there was a lot of “noise” in the search results, and what they considered unnecessary steps in concept-definition. Furthermore their high expectations to searching using AI-powered search with such an inviting interface were not met, particularly the information specialists experienced shelving their professional approach to the search and adopting “an anything goes” approach in an attempt to get useful results from the system.

Yewno.discover was praised for its user-friendly interface and the graphics easily created an understandable overview of terms and relationships, perfect for a newcomer to a research field or topic. It was pointed out by several participants that the biggest problems with Yewno.discover are 1) it is only possible to search two concepts at a time and therefore the possibility of combining multiple terms to specify the search is deficient, and 2) even when the system indicates a relationship between concepts on the knowledge map, there are not necessarily any publications in the system investigating these concepts.

Considering whether participants would use Iris.ai a second time and whether it can be used as part of a research or teaching portfolio, it is also a resounding ‘no thank you’. Both researchers and information specialists explained, that the lack of transparency is the main cause of their unwillingness to use Iris.ai again in particular the issue of research integrity was repeatedly raised. Lack of transparency was discussed in regards to how a search is translated in the system, how the algorithms that include/exclude concepts are implemented, how the problem statement is used and terms weighted to identify publications, and how publications are judged relevant by the system and ranked. Citations from the participants sum up the search experience in Iris.ai as “Iris is too time-consuming and inaccurate” and “time is better used in Google Scholar”.

Five out of six of the participants who searched Yewno.discover would like to use Yewno.discover again, but with a view to only using it in the exploratory phase of a search and thus as part of the [quote]“initial exploration of the literature.” that would be useful for students ..” as they could gain a lot of inspiration”. However the opportunities in Yewno were considered by one participant as “... too limited for serious searches”. In summary, the majority of the participants believe that they could see Yewno.discover as part of their teaching portfolio, but they emphasize that they first must have gain experience and greater knowledge of the software to understand what is going on under the hood (transparency), gain confidence in the stability of the system and have more time to develop best practices regarding documenting search conducted in an AI-system.

New challenges to professionalism

The participants did not consider either Iris.ai or Yewno.discover as efficient ways to search. The AI-systems are designed to encourage discovery and even though the participants acknowledged that the AI-systems could and should not be compared to conventional databases such as PubMed and Google Scholar, they continued to return to these known systems to verify their search skills, definition of terms and the rationale for the search. Both information specialists and researchers had difficulty deciding when to stop the exploring phase of the search, as the AI-systems do not support a systematic approach to searching, there seemed to be no natural beginning or end. Likewise, concerns were raised over the extent the search “history” or “tactics” were documented in both systems. One participant noted that the systems support discovery, and they would as a rule never document this explorative phase of probing a research area. As such, the documentation facilities in the systems, the footsteps in Yewno.discover and the interactive maps in Iris.ai are good enough. The challenge arises when discovery becomes the main methodology for identifying literature and

accordingly doubts were raised regarding documentation of the Focus phases in Iris.ai, as the participants did not have adequate time to evaluate the excel export over the three Focus phases for completeness and transparency. Searching professionally in Iris.ai or Yewno.discover would require re-skilling, including the development of new search requirements that would provide standardised new definitions of transparency, reproducibility, search protocol fulfillment, requirements to documentation, search tactics, strategies and robustness of the search to guide expectations to this new form of academic searching. This points towards a shift in the professional information seeking paradigm at the library, which we expect will be a requirement in the near future, as reporting standards for searches used in systematic reviews are asking for documentation of how literature identified in “other sources” was found. Most recently, the PRISMA statement (Page et al, 2021) requires reporting of literature found using other methods included in the PRISMA flowchart.

Even though the AI-systems challenged conventional approaches to academic searching and expectations to search methodologies, the systems were observed to encourage new forms of collaboration and dialogue around a research activity. Whereas the control group divided responsibilities according to profiles of information specialists, who conducted the search, and researchers, who judged the definitions of the search terms and relevance of the results, the groups which worked with the AI-systems explored the topic areas together. This form of collaboration could be caused by the “newness” of the AI-system as a product which the participants were curious to explore, but it is worth considering if discovery systems do require an increased interaction, discussion and collaboration within a research “team”.

Expert quality assessment and the quantitative assessment

Without any knowledge of which system, the retrieved publications came from, the expert group unanimously gave the publications identified in the AI-systems a lower quality rating. The expert group came from a wide range of disciplines and academic profiles and accordingly, we do not consider the expert group biased toward one form of communication or research methodology over another. The cause of the low-quality rating could be the type of scientific communication identified in the systems. Predominantly more non-original research publications were found in Yewno.discover, such as meeting reports, editorials and opinion papers, whereas the control group found original papers which our rating system perhaps biased the assessment towards. The wide publication type is not necessarily a weakness of the AI-system. Yewno.discover includes grey literature and non-original works that can be very accessible and easier digestible at the discovery phase of the search, especially to a novice in a research area. Further, as pointed out by the Institut for Work and Health ...”because they [grey literature] aren't tied to a conventional structure, they can be longer and provide more detail.”²

Further, the quantitative assessment showed that AI-systems did indeed support the visibility of Open Access publications, which is an area of strategic interest at the University Library. The assessment showed that the publications found in the AI-system experimented with other forms of peer review, such as fast-track review and open-peer review. These forms of peer-review means that papers can potentially be published more quickly and the peer review process is more transparent, thus bringing new research to the forefront in the AI-systems. However, it is important to determine whether or not the innovations in peer review and the speed in which publications are published have effect on their quality and content (Barroga, 2020). Barroga points to a potential increase in replication studies, malpractice and low-quality papers or conversely, a potential improvement of

² <https://www.iwh.on.ca/what-researchers-mean-by/grey-literature>

the quality of papers and speed of publication. At the present time, we conclude, that searching in AI-systems requires the searcher has competencies in both source criticism and scientific integrity (good conduct of research).

Limitations

The Hackathon is an artificial test environment that brought together participants that do not normally work together and were expected to complete a search activity in four hours that is normally conducted over weeks. During the Hackathon the participants had to understand a case, formulate a research question, conduct a search and identify relevant literature. Time is a factor that may have affected the participants, thoroughness of the search, decisions and humour towards the end of the Hackathon-day.

The participants were placed in teams where their individual knowledge of the research case and skills in searching could have caused bias between the groups' level or expertise and the extent the groups can be compared. Some groups had a stronger disciplinary knowledge than others, likewise some had more experience in working together as a research team.

Iris.ai and Yewno.discover are two very different systems that should not be compared on the same parameters of systematicity and efficiency. However, both Iris.ai and Yewno.discover are aimed at researchers in the early phase of their project. Whereas Iris.ai combines process tools to map out an overall landscape and build a reading list, Yewno.discover is designed to develop questions in research projects and get the user to think about the vocabulary they use to frame their work. Our test set-up allowed the participants, information specialists and researchers to explore each product without specific tasks that restricted their experiences in each product. The findings may not apply to students, who were not represented in the Hackathon.

Conclusions

The AI-systems enabled a fast search across thousands of documents which resulted in "knowledge maps" that visualized the interdisciplinarity of a research area, concepts and related literature. It is possible to identify new, unexpected relationships and challenge one's preconception of a hypothesis. Further, AI-systems make Open Access publications and other forms of scientific communication visible in the search. However, the tested AI-systems when compared to traditional search systems such as PubMed, have several weaknesses. There is a lack of transparency in how the search in the AI-system is interpreted, how the algorithms work and which resources are being searched. There are limited functionalities to document the search, limited choice of concepts in Yewno.discover and a very unclear ontology in Iris.ai and how terms are excluded or included in the search. The latter resulted in a lot of "noise" in the search. The systems were not stable during the tests, which points to a lack of maturity in the product.

We questioned if the AI-powered systems were more efficient than traditional search resources. It was perhaps not fair to pose that question, as we have learned through the Hackathon, we should not compare discovery systems to traditional systems that are built to accommodate a systematic approach to the search. Iris.ai and Yewno.discover are effective tools to explore a topic but are not efficient, transparent or reliable academic search tools.

Discovery systems support the explorative phase of the search and this is the value they have for the user. Iris.ai and Yewno.discover have slightly different values for the researcher and the information

specialist. For the researcher, the AI-systems challenge what they expect to find on a topic. They are used to searching in curated and quality controlled disciplinary specific databases where a search results in a high degree of overlap. Searching in AI-system helped them quickly gain a cross-disciplinary perspective on their research question and hence to some extent challenged their preconceptions. For information specialist, the value was also in gaining an overview of a topic from different perspectives, which they argued would prepare them for a “reference interview” with a student or researcher. Further, the graphical display of the results as an interactive map reduced the complexity of the overview. The expert quality assessment indicated that publications found in Yewno.discover did not live up to expected standards for research quality, particularly trust in the results and conclusions presented in each paper. Consequently, the AI-systems at the present time are not considered mature enough to support expectations and demands to systematic search. As thorough and transparent documentation is not possible, reproducibility is not possible and users have to find new ways to document the search.

In conclusion, the tested AI-powered systems force the user to let go of traditional approaches to search, for example block searches, proximity operators and Boolean logic and broaden our perception of how an academic search can be conducted. Such a reflection can cause a paradigm shift in information seeking practice, that demands new terminology, understandings, standards and expectations to the search and also to the competencies of the searchers. Our hackathon indicates that increased knowledge and skills in system architecture, source criticism and research conduct are essential.

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Table 7: Description of relevant publications and publishing source

Group	Title	Lang	Type	Method	Source	Publisher	Peer review	Reviewer ethics /support	Open Access
1	[A care concept and its contribution to the stability of home-based care arrangements : Cross-sectoral care between vision and reality].	Ger	original article	interview	Z Gerontol Geriatr	Springer	-	-	no
2	Strategies for vaccine-product innovation: Creating an enabling environment for product development to uptake in low- and middle-income countries	Eng	original article	mixed method_case and interview	Vaccine	Elsevier	single-blind	Yes	yes
2	Outbreak response as an essential component of vaccine development	Eng	opinion paper	narrative review	The Lancet: Infectious diseases	Elsevier	single-blind	Yes honarium for fast track;	no
2	Two decades of vaccine innovations for global public good: Report of the Developing Countries' Vaccine Manufacturers Network 20th meeting, 21-23 october 2019, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	Eng	meeting report	discussion summary	Vaccine	Elsevier	single-blind	Yes	yes
2	How New Models Of Vaccine Development For COVID-19 Have Helped Address An Epic Public Health Crisis	Eng	opinion paper	narrative review	Health Affairs	Project Hope	No formal review	NI	yes
2	Impact of COVID-19 on materials science research innovation and related pandemic response	Eng	editorial	introduction to special issue	Materials Research Society Bulletin	Springer	NI	NI	yes
2	Pivoting to online learning—The future of learning and work	Eng	Original article	Case	The journal of Competency-Based Education	Wiley	discontinued	discontinued	no
2	Sudden challenges in teaching ecology and aligned disciplines during a global pandemic: Reflections on the rapid move online and perspectives on moving forward	Eng	original article	online survey	Ecology and Evolution	Wiley	single blind	Yes Open peer review pilot	yes
2	Closure of Universities Due to Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): Impact on Education and Mental Health of Students and Academic Staff	Eng	opinion paper	narrative review	Cureus	Cureus Inc	single-blind; external	N fast review	yes

2	Using Rapid Design Thinking to Overcome COVID-19 Challenges in Medical Education	Eng	opinion paper	narrative review	Academic medicine	Wolters Kluwer	single-blind	Yes	yes
2	Transition of a Collaborative In-Person Health Care Innovation Course to Online Learning	Eng	original article	case study	Journal of Nursing education	Slack Inc	double-blind	NI	no
3	The fall of the innovation empire and its possible rise through open science	Eng	original article	Literature review	Research Policy	Elsevier	double blind	Yes	Yes
4	Effects of COVID-19 on College Students' Mental Health in the United States: Interview Survey Study	Eng	original article	interview survey	Journal of Medical Internet Research	JMIR PUBLICATIONS, INC	single-blind	NI	yes
4	Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on College Student Mental Health and Wellness	Eng	original article	survey/assessment	Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry	Elsevier	double-blind	NI	no
4	Mental health of college students during the COVID-19 epidemic in China	Eng	original article	Online survey	JOURNAL OF AFFECTIVE DISORDERS	Elsevier	single-blind	Yes	no
4	Exploring Perceived Stress among Students in Turkey during the COVID-19 Pandemic	Eng	original article	Cross-sectional /survey	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	MDPI	single-blind	NI	yes
4	Investigating Mental Health of US College Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Cross-Sectional Survey Study	Eng	original article	Online survey	Journal of Medical Internet Research	JMIR PUBLICATIONS, INC	single-blind; external	NI	yes
4	Impact of COVID-19 on Emotional Resilience and Learning Management of Middle School Students	Eng	original article	online survey	medical Science monitor	INT SCIENTIFIC INFORMATION , INC	NI	NI	no
4	Stress, anxiety, and sleep among college and university students during the COVID-19 pandemic	Eng	original article	online survey	JOURNAL OF AMERICAN COLLEGE HEALTH	Taylor Francis	double-blind	Yes	no

**N = no information on the website. Peer reviewers could have access to review policy and ethics through a review submission channel
The shaded publications were not assessed in the expert quality assessment*

Table 8: Bibliometric description of publishing source

Group	Title	PY	WOS research areas	field quartile	IF*	Article IF	Citations	BFI level*
1	[A care concept and its contribution to the stability of home-based care arrangements: Cross-sectoral care between vision and reality].	2021	Geriatrics & Gerontology	Q4	1.311	0.259	0	no
2	Strategies for vaccine-product innovation: Creating an enabling environment for product development to uptake in low- and middle-income countries	2021	Immunology; Research & Experimental Medicine	Q2	3.641	1.207	0	1
2	Outbreak response as an essential component of vaccine development	2019	Infectious diseases	Q1	25.07	10.233	4	2
2	Two decades of vaccine innovations for global public good: Report of the Developing Countries' Vaccine Manufacturers Network 20th meeting, 21-23 October 2019, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil	2020	Immunology; Research & Experimental Medicine	Q2	3.641	1.207	2	1
2	How New Models Of Vaccine Development For COVID-19 Have Helped Address An Epic Public Health Crisis	2021	Health Care Sciences & Services	Q1	6.301	3.840	11	2
2	Impact of COVID-19 on materials science research innovation and related pandemic response	2021	Materials Science; Physics	Q1	6.578	1.446	0	no
2	Pivoting to online learning--The future of learning and work	2021	Discontinued	-	-	-	-	no
2	Sudden challenges in teaching ecology and aligned disciplines during a global pandemic: Reflections on the rapid move online and perspectives on moving forward	2021	Environmental Sciences & Ecology, Evolutionary Biology	Q2	2.881	0.905	0	1
2	Closure of Universities Due to Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): Impact on Education and Mental Health of Students and Academic Staff	2020	General & Internal Medicine	Q3	none	0.263	378	no
2	Using Rapid Design Thinking to Overcome COVID-19 Challenges in Medical Education	2021	Education & Educational ResearchHealth Care Sciences & Services	Q1	6.893	2.708	14	1
2	Transition of a Collaborative In-Person Health Care Innovation Course to Online Learning	2021	Nursing	Q3	1.726	0.532	0	2
3	The fall of the innovation empire and its possible rise through open science	2021	Business & economics	Q1	8.110	2.753	0	2
4	Effects of COVID-19 on College Students' Mental Health in the United States: Interview Survey Study	2020	Medical informatics	Q1	5.428	1.865	240	2
4	Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on College Student Mental Health and Wellness	2021	Psychology/psychiatry	Q1	8.829	3.717	31	2
4	Mental health of college students during the COVID-19 epidemic in China	2021	Psychiatry	Q1	4.839	1.527	20	1
4	Exploring Perceived Stress among Students in Turkey during the COVID-19 Pandemic	2020	Public, environmental, occupational health	Q2	3.390	0.77	20	1

4	Investigating Mental Health of US College Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Cross-Sectional Survey Study	2020	Medical informatics	Q1	5.428	1.865	112	2
4	Impact of COVID-19 on Emotional Resilience and Learning Management of Middle School Students	2020	Research & Experimental Medicine	Q3	2.649	0.493	7	1
4	Stress, anxiety, and sleep among college and university students during the COVID-19 pandemic	2021	Education & Educational Research, Public, Environmental & Occupational Health	Q2	3.093	0.790	1	1

**IF = two year impact factor calculated in Journal Citation Reports. ** BFI – level on the Danish Bibliometric Research Indicator, Autumn 2021*

The shaded publications were not assessed in the expert quality assessment.

